

2,3-BUTANEDIOL PRODUCTION FROM SACCHARIFIED AGRI FOOD MIXED-BIOWASTE BY RECOMBINANT ESCHERICHIA COLI STRAIN

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ABSTRACT: The agricultural industry generates substantial amounts of mixed bio-waste, much of which is rich in organic matter and valuable components but often discarded. Efficient processing and valorization of these plant-based residues represent a valuable opportunity to create high-value compounds. In this study, three secondary streams were nutritionally characterized coming from different feedstocks: wholesale markets (MCV), food and drink industry (NdM) and greenhouses (SACH). Saccharification was carried out, resulting in conversion yields up to 59%, 68% and 43% (w/w) for MCV, NdM and SACH biowaste, equivalent to 20; 15 and 12g/L sugar release, respectively, to be used as the sole carbon source for the production of 2,3-butanediol (2,3-BDO) using a recombinant *E. coli* strain. Metabolic engineering was performed in different *E. coli* strains to express the *Klebsiella oxytoca* α -acetolactate synthase (BudB), α -acetolactate decarboxylase (BudA) and 2,3-butanediol dehydrogenase (BudC) genes. Different culture media compositions were designed, applying different sugar sources obtained by the previous saccharification. In shake flask experiments, the production yield of 2,3-BDO reached a maximum of 3,9 g/L, equivalent to 0,1g of 2,3-BDO per g of glucose, 43 times higher than the obtaining using a commercial culture media. Finally, fermentation in fedbatch mode resulted in a final concentration of 50,3g/L.

Keywords: Agroindustrial residues, biobased products, fermentation, hydrolysis

1 INTRODUCTION

Bio-waste that is generated along the agri-food value chain is an abundant resource with an estimated 113M tons produced annually in the EU [1]. Agri-food waste is a rich source of valuable compounds, such as lignocellulose, starch, polysaccharides, proteins, or polyphenolic constituents with a wide range of applications such as food, feed, cosmetics, bio-based products [2]. Yet, the full potential of these bio-waste streams as a source of recycled components is untapped.

Conventional and advanced state-of-the-art valorization processes require the bio-waste streams to be free from non-organic impurities such as plastic, glass or metal, as otherwise any contamination would prevent further use of the outputs. However, bio-waste streams generated along the agri-food value chain are often mixed with such impurities. Since these contaminants cannot be easily separated due to technical or economic barriers, currently 75% of mixed bio-waste goes to landfill or is incinerated [3]. To tackle these challenges, the MixMatters project has gathered key technology players that, in cooperation with the bio-based industries and bio-waste providers, will work on a breakthrough concept for making technically and economically feasible the separation and valorization of biowaste. The MixMatters Integrated System consists of a Separation Unit and a Valorization Hub. The Separation Unit processes the mixed biowaste in-situ at the waste generation sites and concentrates and stabilizes the recovered streams, free from impurities like plastics or cardboard. The Valorization Hub is a multi-purpose biorefinery that treats and upgrades the streams previously obtained to generate a portfolio of high value-added outputs.

In the frame of this work, our main objective is to convert various mixed-biowastes into two high value-added outputs: sugar concentrates and 2,3-butanediol (2,3-BDO). Sugar concentrates are obtained via a saccharification (enzymatic hydrolysis) of the complex sugars of the bio-waste (starch, cellulose, etc) into simple sugars (glucose, fructose, etc). This sugar concentrate is

used for the formulation of culture media for growing recombinant *E. coli* strains in fermentation processes. 2,3-BDO is a versatile chemical compound utilized across various industries, including agriculture, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals. One of its key advantages is its role as a "chemical building block," enabling the synthesis of a wide range of other valuable chemical compounds.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Characterization of the agri-food biowaste samples

Samples of the three bio-waste streams were provided by MercaValencia (MCV), Natural de Montaña (NdM) and Servicios Ambientales Las Chozas (SACH). Those samples were processed using a shredder and depacker devices in order to generate secondary streams. The organic fractions were centrifugated at 10.000 x g for 10 min at room temperature, and both pellet (solid fraction) and supernatant (liquid fraction) were analyzed for their carbohydrate contents.

The solid fractions were used to perform the saccharification trials and the sugars released were used in the formulation of growing culture media rather than traditional sugar solutions.

The liquid fraction was concentrated by TFF and was also used as carbon source in the culture media formulation

2.2 Saccharification of the solid fraction of the agri-food biowaste

The saccharification process consists of transforming complex sugars (polysaccharides such as starch and lignocellulose) into simple sugars (monosaccharides such as glucose, fructose, etc.) through an enzymatic treatment.

Initial tests of saccharification were carried out in 1L stirred tank bioreactor. For these trials it was considered using 10% load of dry matter. Thus, depending on the moisture of each sample, the humid solid fraction introduced in the reactor was different (MCV: 437g; NdM: 840g; SACH: 342g). The solid fraction was diluted in

acetate buffer (0,1M) until a reaction volume of 1L was reached. 10AUG/g of dry matter corresponding to a blend of amylases, beta-glucanases, pectinases, hemicellulases, xylanases, proteases and cellulases (Novozymes, Novogenesis) was used (Table I). The temperature of the process was 58°C, the pH was set to 4,5-5,5 and an initial agitation of 200-900 rpm was applied to dilute the solid fraction in the buffer and was set to 450rpm during the 48h process. Samples were taken at 24h and end-time. Glucose concentration was analyzed using Y15 analyzer from Biosystems.

Table I: Enzymes and volume used in the saccharification trials

Enzyme	Volume (mL)
Amylase AG XXL	2,2
BAN 480L	2,2
Viscozyme L	3,3
ProEx	2,2
Celluclast 1,5L	2,2
Ultraflo XL	2,4
Saczyme Yield	1,3

2.3 2,3-butanediol production using recombinant *E. coli* strain.

2.3.1 Genetic construction of recombinant *E. coli* strain

The 2,3-butanediol biosynthesis from pyruvate is depicted in Figure 1. Initially, the genetic chassis required to produce 2,3-butanediol was constructed *in silico*. This chassis was composed of the genes *BudB* (GenBank: CAA0277316.1) and *BudA* (NCBI Reference Sequence: WP_014226712.1), both regulated by a medium-strength promoter (BBa_J23114), and *BudC* (NCBI Reference Sequence: WP_014226712.1), regulated by a strong promoter (BBa_J23115). All the genes were regulated under the terminator BBa_B1001 (Fig. 2). The genes were sourced from *Klebsiella oxytoca*, and promoters and the terminator were selected from the publicly available Anderson promoter's library (iGEM).

Figure 1: 2,3-butanediol biosynthesis produced from pyruvate

The genes were cloned in tandem and subsequently introduced into two different expression vectors to evaluate the production efficiency across different plasmid backbones. The plasmids tested included a modification of the commercially available pUC57 and a custom-designed plasmid developed by AINIA (Fig. 3).

Figure 2: Genetic construction to express *BudB* (acetolactate synthase), *BudA* (acetolactate decarboxylase), and *BudC* (2,3-butanediol dehydrogenase) in recombinant *E. coli* strains.

Following the construction of the two different genetic chassis, two *E. coli* strains were transformed: (i) the commercially available *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) *pLysS* and (ii) *E. coli* W, known for its ability to metabolize complex sugars, which is advantageous for utilizing alternative substrates. Transformants were screened for the expression of the 2,3-BDO and positive clones were selected for further experiments. Metabolic pathway optimization (data not show) was carried out to enhance production yields.

Figure 3: Transformed *E. coli* strains based on the plasmids used: BM119, BM125, BM116, BM124.

2.3.2 Culture media formulation from agri-food waste for the production of 2,3-butanediol.

To test the engineered strains, alternative sugar substrate from agri-food biowaste was used to check the production of 2,3-BDO. These culture media were formulated using the liquid fraction from MCV secondary stream (Table II). MM-01 was supplemented with mineral solutions in order to enhance the growth of *E. coli*. MM-02 is MM-01 two-fold diluted in order to avoid a hypothetical inhibition by excess of sugars substrate. The commercial M9 media was used as positive control for *E. coli* fermentation and 2,3-BDO production yield. Shake flask experiments were initially carried out at 37°C, 200 rpm for 48h and samples were taken every 24 hours. In AMBR mini reactors (250 mL working volume), a fed-batch culture was carried out during 72h using a feeding solution with a sugar concentration of 200 g/L. Every 15h, 20 mL of feeding was pumped to increase the sugar concentration. The pH was maintained using 1M NaOH.

The production of 2,3-butanediol was quantified throughout gas chromatography at 24 and 48h production times. The 3 stereoisomers (dextro-, levo-, and meso-forms) were identified and quantified compared to an analytical standard, mixture of racemic and meso forms (2,3-BDO is eluted at 7.03 ± 0.06 min).

Table II: Glucose and fructose content of the different formulated mediums.

Media	Glucose (g/L)	Fructose (g/L)
MM-01	40,76	42,8
MM-02	20,29	19,25
M9	19,97	0

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Nutritional characterization

The different secondary streams from MCV, NdM, and SACH were analyzed, and their nutritional profile is given in Fig. 4. Results show a great heterogeneity in carbohydrate content between the samples, starch: 16; 0; 8 % (w/w), cellulose: 15; 20; 16 % (w/w), hemicellulose: 20; 27; 14 % (w/w) and lignin: 6; 15; 8 % (w/w) contents for MCV, NdM and SACH respectively. This nutritional profile is subjected to change depending on the nature of the sample itself due to the seasonality (winter/summer fruits and vegetables) and the type of waste discarded on the day of collection (e.g. Bananas, peaches, watermelon, etc). However, the results show that even depending on the variability between the three bio-waste streams and the variability they may have over time, they all contain complex sugars that may be susceptible to saccharification. Moreover, the liquid fractions contained some free sugars which correspond to a glucose concentration of 16,18; 11,71; 2,41 g/L and fructose concentration of 15,82; 13,27; 2,63 g/L for MCV, NdM and SACH, respectively.

Figure 4: Nutritional characterization of the dry solid fraction from the three bio-waste streams.

3.2 Saccharification of the solid fraction of the agri-food biowaste

The glucose concentration over time during the saccharification process is shown in Figure 5. Fructose release was not observed and remained the same over the time of saccharification. MCV and SACH samples homogenized properly during the initial stirring phase but the amount of NdM solid fraction was probably too large, preventing proper dissolution in the buffer. That caused the blockage of the sampling, and it was not possible to take sample during the process.

Figure 5: Evolution of glucose released in the saccharification process

The starch and cellulose to glucose conversion yields are given in Table III. Results show that saccharification were not complete and that not all the glucose has been released: 13,9; 7,06; 15,9 g/L for MCV, NdM and SACH respectively.

Table III: Saccharification yields (%). Glucose obtained from the initial cellulose and starch of dry samples.

Sample	Glucose yields
MCV	59%
NdM	68%
SACH	43%

3.3 2,3-butanediol production using recombinant *E. coli*

The 2,3-BDO production (g/L) obtained using the different recombinant strains grown in MM-01 and MM-02 culture media (shake flask experiments) is presented in Table IV and compared to the production yield achieved using M9 culture media, which served as a positive control.

Results show that the four recombinant strains were able to produce 2,3-BDO using the nutrients of the three culture media. However, BM-119 and BM-124 achieved the highest production (3,9 and 3,7 g/L respectively), reaching 0,1g of 2,3-butanediol per g of glucose. These results are consistent with the literature, where similar yields have been reported in shake flask culture [4,5]. Moreover, it has also been demonstrated that the alternative culture media formulated from bio-waste (MM1 and MM2) provided better concentration and yields of 2,3-butanediol production than commercial M9 medium. When the fermentation process was carried out in reactor, in fed-batch mode, the 2,3-BDO has been considerably improved to reach the final concentration of 50,3g/L. Compared to 15,0 g/L and 26,6 g/L obtained from banana peels and whole bananas, respectively [6] or to 42,9 and 35,5 g/L obtained by fed-batch culture (*E. Ludwigii*) from pure arabinose and Sugar beet pulp hydrolysate, respectively [7], as well as 18 g/L obtained from cheese whey by a non-engineered mutant strain of *L. lactis* [8], our results show the high potential for recovery

of the three types of feedstock used in this study.

Strain	2,3-butanediol production (g/L)		
	MM-01	MM-02	M9
BM-116	1.3	1.3	0.4
BM-119	3.9	1.6	0.4
BM-124	3.7	1.9	0.3
BM-125	2.5	1.0	0.2
Strain	Yield of 2,3-butandiol (g)/glucose (g)		
BM-116	0.04	0.09	0.02
BM-119	0.1	0.1	0.02
BM-124	0.1	0.1	0.02
BM-125	0.08	0.07	0.01

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In this study, we have set up a saccharification process from three different mixed organic wastes. The saccharification yields obtained were 59%, 68% and 43% for MCV, NdM and SACH biowaste respectively. The yields resulted in glucose concentration of 20; 15; 12 g/L respectively. Different recombinant *E. coli* strains have been engineered to produce 2,3-BDO and the highest concentration achieved up to date —under varying feedstocks and fermentation conditions is 50,3 g/L. Future trials will focus on the optimization of the saccharification process to maximize the release of sugars by evaluating (i) different enzymes combinations; (ii) substrate/enzyme ratio definition, and (iii) the effect of washing step and biomass reused during the process. Further advancements in process optimization and metabolic pathway engineering are also essential to achieve higher titers, yields, and overall productivity. Expanding and optimizing the current system boundaries can contribute to reducing environmental impacts and lowering production costs of 2,3-BDO. Enhancements in fermentation process and downstream processing stages will lead to increased 2,3-BDO titers and significantly reduced overall production costs and associated environmental burdens.

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